

ELECTRONIC CIRCUITS EMBEDDED INTO COMPOSITE AEROSPACE MATERIALS

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INTRODUCTION

This poster presents a concept demonstrator for embedding a complex multi-layer 4-way RF switching network into an aerospace composite material.

CIRCUIT DESCRIPTION

The four-port switch schematic is presented on FIG. 1. The RF part (FIG. 1a) of the circuit consists of:

- broadband single-pole-double-throw switches F2972 (SW1 – SW3)
- RF signal microstrip lines (MSL1 – MSL7) (50 Ω)
- decoupling capacitors (C1 – C9)
- input and output SMA connectors (J1 – J5)

Control part of the switch (FIG. 1b) includes:

- level shifter circuit (R1-R12, C10-C17) – TTL to LVTTTL levels
- voltage regulator (TLV713) (3.3 V)

FIG. 1. RF switch (a) and its control circuit (b)

MEASUREMENT RESULTS

FIG. 4. The measurement and simulation results for four-way switch embedded into aerospace composite structure

DEVICE FABRICATION

- The switch composite structure in FIG. 2 is made with HexPly 914E structural glass (S-Glass) pre-preg plies and cured in the autoclave (T = 177 °C at 700 kPa pressure).
- Microstrips, control tracks, blind and buried vias and ground plane have been made using both non-woven carbon-nickel-copper veil and silver conducting ink.
- RF components of the switch are buried inside the composite.
- SMA connectors are bonded using conductive silver epoxy.

FIG. 2. Exploded view of the composite RF switch

FIG. 3. Fabricated switch

CONCLUSION

- A new technique for embedding active RF circuits into aerospace composites structure has been developed.
- The measurement data shows excellent agreement with simulations.
- The performance of the semiconductor devices was not affected by harsh, long-term, thermal conditions during multiple curing processes.